

BEHAVIOUR OF CHLORONITROBENZENES WITH HYDRAZINE AND HYDRAZINE DERIVATIVES. PART X. PREPARATION OF SOME NITROPHENYLHYDRAZINES AND THEIR HYDRAZONES

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3:4-Dibromo-6-nitro-, 2:3-dibromo-4:6-dinitro- and 2-bromo-3-chloro-4:6-dinitro-phenylhydrazines have been obtained by replacing a halogen or a nitro group by a hydrazine ($-NH-NH_2$) group. The corresponding hydrazones have also been prepared.

In the previous communications (Joshi *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 34; 1952, 29, 46; 1959, 36, 417, 505), the preparation of a number of nitrophenylhydrazines has been described. In this paper, 3:4-dibromo-6-nitro-, 2:3-dibromo-4:6-dinitro- and 2-bromo-3-chloro-4:6-dinitro-phenylhydrazines have been synthesised by the action of hydrazine hydrate on 3:4-dibromo-1:6-dinitro- (Austen, *Ber.*, 1875, 8, 1182), 1:2:3-tribromo-4:6-dinitro- (Joshi and Saxena, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 598) and 1:3-dichloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitro- (Joshi and Saxena, *loc. cit.*) benzenes.

The structures of the hydrazine derivatives follow from the method of their synthesis. Nitrophenylhydrazines are all coloured crystalline compounds. These are quite reactive and easily combine with carbonyl compounds to form the corresponding phenylhydrazones.

* EXPERIMENTAL

3:4-Dibromo-6-nitrophenylhydrazine.—3:4-Dibromo-1:6-dinitrobenzene, dissolved in an excess of ethanol, was treated with an equivalent quantity of hydrazine hydrate. On cooling, a coloured crystalline solid began to separate. After about 24 hours the mass was collected. It was recrystallised from an excess of ethanol as orange-red crystals (75%), m.p. 204°. (Found: C, 23.0; H, 1.4; N, 13.3; Br, 51.2. $C_6H_5O_2N_3Br_2$ requires C, 23.1; H, 1.6; N, 13.5; Br, 51.4%.)

2:3-Dibromo-4:6-dinitrophenylhydrazine was also obtained when a solution of 1:2:3-tribromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene in ethanol was treated with an equimolecular quantity of hydrazine hydrate, and kept overnight. Dibromodinitrophenylhydrazine separating was slightly soluble in ethanol and crystallised from an excess of the solvent in greenish yellow crystals (72%), m.p. 201°. (Found: C, 20.1; H, 1.0; N, 15.3; Br, 44.6. $C_6H_4O_4N_4Br_2$ requires C, 20.2; H, 1.1; N, 15.7; Br, 44.9%.)

2-Bromo-3-chloro-4:6-dinitrophenylhydrazine was prepared similarly by taking an equivalent quantity of 1:3-dichloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene in place of 1:2:3-tribromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene. The phenylhydrazine was also slightly soluble in ethanol. It was crystallised from an excess of it in dirty yellow crystals (69%), m.p. 194°. (Found: C, 22.8; H, 1.2; N, 17.6; Br + Cl, 36.8. $C_6H_4O_4N_4BrCl$ requires C, 23.1; H, 1.3; N, 17.9; Br + Cl, 37.0%.)

Preparation of Phenylhydrazones.—The hydrazones were obtained in nearly quantitative yields by refluxing for 4 to 5 minutes a mixture of the phenylhydrazine (0.5 g.) in ethanol (5 c.c.) and equimolecular proportions of the carbonyl compounds in presence of 1 to 2 drops of H_2SO_4 (cont.). These were purified by recrystallisation from an excess of ethanol or ethyl acetate. Characteristics of hydrazones prepared are recorded in Table I.

* All melting points recorded are uncorrected

TABLE I

S. Carbonyl No. compound.	3:4-Dibromo-6-NP.			2:3-Dibromo-4:6-DNP.			2-Bromo-3-chloro-4:6-DNP.							
	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	% Bromine. Found. Calc.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	% Bromine. Found. Calc.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	% Br + Cl. Found. Calc.		
1. Acetone	151°	Orange	$C_6H_8O_4N_2Br_2$	45.1	45.5	Fale yellow	$C_6H_8O_4N_2Br_2$	40.2	40.4	141°	Lemon-yellow	$C_6H_8O_4N_2BrCl$	32.6	32.8
2. Ethyl methyl ketone	99°	Reddish orange	$C_{10}H_{14}O_2N_2Br_2$	43.7	43.8	Lemon-yellow	$C_{10}H_{14}O_2N_2Br_2$	38.7	39.0	99°	Yellow	$C_{10}H_{14}O_2N_2BrCl$	31.5	31.6
3. Acetophenone	158°	Orange	$C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2Br_2$	38.4	38.7	Yellow	$C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2Br_2$	34.8	34.9	188°	Canary-yellow	$C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2BrCl$	27.4	2.79
4. Benzaldehyde	237°	Brick-red	$C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2$	40.0	40.1	Do	$C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2$	35.8	36.0	221°	Do	$C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2BrCl$	28.5	28.9
5. Salicylaldehyde	280°	Light orange	$C_{14}H_{10}O_3N_2Br_2$	38.4	38.5	Yellowish orange	$C_{14}H_{10}O_3N_2Br_2$	34.6	34.7	225°	Light orange	$C_{14}H_{10}O_3N_2BrCl$	27.6	27.8
6. <i>p</i> -Ethylacetophenone	170°	Reddish orange	$C_{16}H_{18}O_2N_2Br_2$	36.0	36.2									
7. 2-Chloro-5-methylaceto-phenone	161°	Yellowish orange	$C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_2Br_2Cl$	Br & Cl 42.1	42.3									
8. 2:5-Dichloroacetophenone	173°	Yellow	$C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2Cl_2$	Br & Cl 47.6	47.9					204°	Yellow	$C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2BrCl_2$	38.4	38.6
9. <i>p</i> -Methylacetophenone	122°	Yellowish orange	$C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2Br_2$	37.2	37.4									

NP denotes nitrophenylhydrazones.
DNP denotes dinitrophenylhydrazones.

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